

COESO

connecting research and society

COLLABORATIVE ENGAGEMENT ON SOCIETAL ISSUES

WP2 – Open Call texts and rules

Open Call – Guide for Applicants

30 November 2021

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SwafS-27-2020 - Hands-on citizen science and frugal innovation, under Grant Agreement No.101006325

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Deliverable D2.1

Open Call - Guide for Applicants

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1. INTRODUCTION

The [COESO project](#) (Collaborative Engagement on Societal Issues) launches an **Open Call** to fund **5 pilot projects** to implement **innovative Citizen Science projects in Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH)**, inviting civil society and researchers to apply.

This Guide is the main source of information for the Open Call – **COESO-CALL-2021** – and contains the relevant information to guide applicants in preparing and submitting a project proposal.

In case of conflict with other sources of information, the content of this document will prevail as the official and binding information.

For questions regarding the application process, please consult the COESO project website – [Open Call](#) – or contact us at coeso.opencall@cria.org.pt / (+351) 210 464 057.

2. WHAT IS THE COESO PROJECT AND WHAT KIND OF PROJECTS ARE WE SEARCHING FOR?

COESO is a research project, coordinated by the [École des hautes études en sciences sociales](#) (EHESS) and its research unit [OpenEdition](#) Centre, dedicated to the development of citizen science and participatory research in the area of Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH). It consists of 15 partners, from 6 European countries (France, Portugal, Italy, Spain, Belgium and Germany), including research centres, foundations, companies and associations.

COESO is based on a dual approach. First, it provides a framework for the development of pilot participatory projects from different disciplines within the SSH (such as History, Philosophy, Political Science, Sociology and Anthropology) that involve artists, journalists, non-governmental organisations (NGO), small and medium-sized enterprises (SME), national and regional authorities, or local communities. Secondly, it supports the development of a digital platform to facilitate collaboration between researchers and society.

Five pilots have already been selected, covering six disciplines (Anthropology, Philosophy, Performance Studies, Political Science, Sociology and History), involving NGOs, artists, journalists, policymakers and lay citizens¹.

COESO intends to prototype the most common forms of participatory research within the SSH fields, highlight the issues these collaborations can raise in comparison with other disciplinary fields outside the SSH, and suggest solutions to resolve these issues.

¹ For more information about the current pilots please consult the COESO website: <https://coeso.hypotheses.org/pilots>.

To this end, COESO intends to implement a collaborative platform called VERA (Virtual Ecosystem for Research Activation) that will enhance the cooperation and mutual learning practices between citizens and researchers.

COESO follows the [European Citizen Science Association \(ECSA\) 10 Principles of Citizen Science](#) approach to citizen science.

We are looking for projects that meet all the following criteria:

- **Collaborative projects** connecting at least one **researcher** and one **stakeholder** outside academia (civil society organizations, socioeconomic actors, policymakers or other);
- Projects involving **Social Sciences and Humanities disciplines**;
- Projects that follow **participatory research methodology** (non-academic participants are involved at least in the problem definition and data collection, the methodology for data collection and analysis may be research driven) or **collaborative research methodology** (all the participants are involved in problem identification, data collection and analysis);
- Projects willing to be part of an observation protocol and a testing phase for the development of a **platform aimed at supporting and facilitating participatory and collaborative research practices**;
- **Projects** addressing societal challenges (concerning at least one of the [Sustainable Development Goals](#) (SDG));
- **Projects** implemented between a minimum of **6 months** and a maximum of **12 months**.

The following criteria will also be appraised:

- **Participatory projects** that comply with the [ECSA 10 Principles of Citizen Science](#);
- Projects involving **international collaboration** are welcome but not mandatory;
- COESO will give preference to proposals that are committed to making their data available for reuse, following an **open science approach**, for which COESO will provide technical, legal and operational support to successful applicants. In addition, COESO may require citizen science pilots funded to collect, manage and share data with the COESO team.

Proposals should therefore include concrete plans for collaboration and exchange of knowledge, demonstrating how these activities will add significant value to the research.

3. WHY APPLY?

COESO aims to provide a connection between a community of people and initiatives, responding to similar societal challenges and contributing to common goals.

It also encourages participants to be part of the co-definition of research issues, production of knowledge, co-creation of tools to support and assess collaboration between researchers and citizens and in the final usages of the research outputs – funded projects will be part of an experimental protocol to participate in the testing of the **VERA platform** (Virtual Ecosystem for Research Activation) in the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH).

For researchers, this can be an opportunity to collect new types of data, access new research fields, develop new research methods, **enhance the production of new knowledge** and maximize the societal benefit of the research.

For socioeconomic actors, this can be an opportunity to participate in the definition of issues in research projects, **participate in knowledge exchange**, capitalize on and share experiences in their fields.

For policymakers, this can add valuable inputs to **elaborate policies** that are closer to social actors' concerns, increasing the contribution of Social Sciences and Humanities research to innovation.

For Citizens, this may provide an opportunity to contribute to enrich the public debate through evidence-based inputs (involvement and experiences), **participating in civic empowerment**.

4. WHO CAN APPLY?

Applicants must be **legal entities** such as, but not limited to, Civil Society Organizations (CSO), Non-Governmental Organizations (NGO), Higher Education Institutions, Research Centres and Small and Medium Enterprises (SME).

Funding is only available to organizations that are legally established in EU Member States including their outermost regions or associated countries eligible to receive [Horizon 2020](#) grants, provided that the applicants are not covered by the Council sanctions in force.

Consortia can apply as long as they do not consist exclusively of members from academia or exclusively from civil society.

Eligibility criteria will apply individually to each consortium participant. When participating as a consortium, the parties must choose the entity that will be the sole legal representative (project proponent/leader) and that will submit the proposal/application and commit to COESO on behalf of the consortium.

Collaborations should be meaningful for all partners involved and enable joint learning throughout the duration of the project and beyond.

5. HOW TO APPLY?

Applicants should read the **Guide for applicants** as well as **FAQ** and other complementary information available on COESO and CRIA websites.

The application and selection process will have **two rounds**:

In the **first-round** applicants are invited to submit a **Short Proposal** containing a brief description of the project purpose, objectives, team and budget.

Successful applicants selected in the first-round will be invited to submit a **Full Project Proposal** within the **second-round**.

APPLICATION PROCESS:

Applicants must read the mandatory rules and criteria carefully and prepare the submission proposals according to the instructions.

Application Mandatory Rules:

- Applications must be submitted in English. Submissions made in any other language will not be considered.
- Applications must be readable, accessible and printable.
- The proposal template cannot be changed or altered in any way.
- All requested documents will be submitted electronically in PDF format.
- Applications must be complete and contain all mandatory parts and supporting documents. Only complete applications will be considered for selection/evaluation.
- Proposals must be received by the Call closing date and time. Late proposals, or proposals submitted to any other address or by any means other than those indicated in this guide, will not be considered.
- Upon reception of the proposal, applicants will receive an acknowledgement receipt.
- Once a proposal is submitted, applicants can no longer modify it or retrieve uploaded documents for further editing or updates.

All applications must be sent **by e-mail** to: coeso.opencall@cria.org.pt.

The application process consists of sending the completed proposal template, as well as the mandatory documents required for each round, as presented in the following section.

FIRST ROUND – SHORT PROPOSAL

- Download and complete the **Short Proposal template**
- Send the Short Proposal and all the required documents **by e-mail** (by 30 January 2022)

Short Proposal

The list of required contents and documents for the Short Proposal is as follows:

CONTENTS	DOCUMENTS
Description of the main idea Team Impact Activities Project duration and Budget	Official document proving the legal nature of the applicant and/or the consortium members Copy of the consortium agreement (if applicable) Document proving the applicant's/ consortium members' establishment in one of the eligible countries

SECOND ROUND – FULL PROJECT PROPOSAL

- Download and complete the **Full Project Proposal** template
- Send the Full Project Proposal and all the required documents **by e-mail** (by 31 March 2022)

Full Project Proposal

The list of mandatory contents and documents for the Full Project Proposal is as follows:

CONTENTS	DOCUMENTS
Project rationale Project purpose and objectives Relevance to the call Data management Team Impact Work plan Activities Project duration and Budget List of deliverables (including a final report)	List of persons (permanent and non-permanent staff) involved in the Project Document evidencing that the applicant's team includes at least one researcher and one non-academic stakeholder Declaration of acceptance (Vera Platform) Document evidencing powers of attorney/ representation powers of the proposal signatory and/or Consortium representative Conflict of interest declaration

6. HOW WILL THE PROPOSALS BE SELECTED?

Applications that meet all the requirements will be evaluated by the COESO-team with the assistance of an external jury – COESO [Advisory Board](#) –, according to the criteria indicated in the following section. Applications that do not meet one or more mandatory requirements will be excluded from the selection phase and their respective applicants will be notified accordingly by email.

All proposals submitted to the Open Call will be treated equally: they are evaluated impartially based on their merits, irrespective of their origin or the identity of the applicants.

The proposals selected for funding must demonstrate high quality in the context and criteria set out in this Open call.

Diversity is the leading principle driving the selection of the projects. One of the main purposes is to obtain a balanced list of selected projects, in terms of geography, socioeconomic background, disciplines, types of stakeholders involved, issues addressed and gender.

Please note that applicants may exercise the right to be heard in regard to decisions taken during the selection procedure, via e-mail sent to coeso.opencall@cria.org.pt within 10 business days of their notification of any decision.

FIRST ROUND – SHORT PROPOSAL

□ ELIGIBILITY CRITERIA

Short Proposal selection will consist of verifying that the following criteria are met:

CRITERIA	Check (Yes/No)
1. Type of applicant	Y/N
2. Collaborative project	Y/N
3. Countries eligible for funding	Y/N
4. SSH disciplines	Y/N
5. SDG addressed	Y/N
6. Project duration	Y/N
7. Budget adequacy	Y/N

In case of non-eligible applications, where the mandatory criteria identified above are not met, applicants will be notified that the application was not successful in the Call (with express indication of reasons 1 to 7).

EVALUATION CRITERIA

The second stage of the selection process for the first round consists of the evaluation of the quality of the Short Proposals according to the following criteria:

CRITERIA		SCORING
Excellence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Clarity and pertinence of the objectives - Credibility and adequacy of the proposed approach - Ambition, potential innovation (groundbreaking objectives, novel concepts and approaches) engagement with COESO's vision, the FAIR movement, ECSA principles) - Development of (new) methodologies 	1 - 5
Impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Potential impact of the proposal and how this can be carried out within the COESO 	1 - 5

	vision/objectives - Potential impact on civic empowerment, society, production of new knowledge - Clear identification of target groups - Social benefit of the project for the targeted groups	
Implementation	Coherence and effectiveness of the work plan, including relevance of allocation of tasks and resources Consistency of the description of the action and its suitability for the proposal - Methodology and work plan - Viability of the project and budget adequacy	1 – 5

The outcome of the evaluation will be a ranked list of all the proposals, based on the scores obtained by each proposal.

The evaluation team will rank the application, assigning a **score from 1 to 5** for each criterion, and produce an **Individual Evaluation Report**.

The final score will be an average of the individual assessments made by the Experts.

The highest ranked proposal may not be selected if there are relevant reasons to reject a specific application and/or applicant. In this case, the choice will pass to the next-ranked proposal.

In case all the proposals are ranked below the **minimum evaluation score of 3**, none will be selected.

If applicable, the following selection criteria will apply to determine a priority order amongst proposals evaluated with the same score. For applications with the same score, the one with the highest score in the Excellence criteria will prevail.

After completion of the evaluation process, a **public summary report** will be published on the project website, where the applicants will be informed of the evaluation ranking and results.

Applicants whose Short Proposals meet all the defined criteria will receive a written communication (e-mail) indicating that they have been selected for the next round of the selection process.

Successful applicants selected in the first-round will be invited to submit a Full Project Proposal within the second-round.

SECOND ROUND – FULL PROJECT PROPOSAL

□ ELIGIBILITY CRITERIA

At this stage, the aim is to verify whether the submitted application meets all the applicable requirements:

REQUIREMENTS	Check Yes/No
1. Maintenance of previous eligibility criteria in the application	Y/N
2. Proof of the existence of one researcher and one non-academic stakeholder in the project team	Y/N
3. Relevance to the Call	Y/N
4. Detailed Work Plan	Y/N
5. Project duration (minimum of 6 months and maximum of 12 months)	Y/N
6. Budget up to €50,000.00.	Y/N
7. Declaration of acceptance for participation on the VERA Platform	Y/N
8. Declaration of non-conflict of interest	Y/N

In case of non-fulfilment of mandatory application criteria, the applicants will be notified that the application was not successful in the Call (with express indication of reasons 1 to 8).

EVALUATION CRITERIA

The final stage of the selection process for the second round consists in the evaluation of the quality of the proposals according to the following criteria:

CRITERIA		SCORING
Excellence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Clarity and pertinence of the objectives - Credibility and adequacy of the proposed approach - Ambition, potential innovation (groundbreaking objectives, novel concepts and approaches) engagement with COESO's vision, the FAIR movement, ECSA principles) - Development of (new) methodologies 	1 - 5

Impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Potential impact of the proposal and how this can be carried out within the COESO vision/objectives - Potential impact on civic empowerment, society, production of new knowledge - Clear identification of target groups - Social benefit of the project for the targeted groups 	1 - 5
Implementation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Coherence and effectiveness of the work plan, including relevancy of allocation of tasks and resources - Consistency of the description of the action and its suitability for the proposal - Methodology and work plan - Viability of the project and budget adequacy 	1 - 5

The outcome of the evaluation will be a ranked list of all proposals, based on the scores obtained by each proposal.

The evaluation team will rank the application, assigning a **score from 1 to 5** for each criterion, and produce an Individual Evaluation Report.

The final score will be an average of the individual assessments made by the Experts.

The highest ranked proposal may not be selected in case there are relevant reasons to reject a specific application and/or applicant. In this case, the choice will pass to the next-ranked proposal.

In case all the proposals are ranked below the **minimum evaluation score of 3**, none will be selected.

If applicable, the following selection criteria will apply to determine a priority order amongst proposals evaluated with the same score.

For applications with the same score, the one with the highest score in the Excellence criteria will prevail.

After completion of the evaluation process, a **public summary report** will be published on the project website, where the applicants will be informed of the evaluation ranking and results.

The project proposals with the **5 highest scores** will receive a written communication (e-mail) indicating that they have been selected for funding.

The list of selected projects will be published on the COESO and CRIA websites.

A lump sum will be provided for the selected projects that follow the eligibility criteria. All types of activities described in the implementation of the work plan and related to the objectives of the project will be eligible for funding, as long as it is demonstrated that the activity is serving the project (and not for personal use or interest).

The list of possible eligible activities includes (but it's not limited to):

- Fieldwork
- Knowledge exchange activities
- Workshops
- Dissemination actions
- Public engagement activities

7. FUNDING / FINANCIAL SUPPORT

Total funding amount for the Call: **€250,000.00**

Maximum funding per project: **€50,000.00**

The financial support received by the selected applicants will be in the form of a **lump sum** of up to 50,000.00 euros.

The lump sum is a simplified method of settling expenses in projects financed by Horizon 2020 funds. This means that the funded project is not required to present strictly defined accounting documents to prove the cost incurred (e.g., invoices), but is obliged to demonstrate the implementation of the project in line with its established deliverables. The payment is exclusively based on completion of activity and on a technical report of results (no financial reporting is required). The lump sum does not release applicants from the obligation to collect documentation to confirm the costs under fiscal regulations.

Activities carried out with COESO cannot receive double funding. Synergies with other sources of funding, including other Horizon2020 projects, are encouraged as long as the grants are used for complementary and not overlapping purposes.

The selected projects will receive the full amount of the budget requested for the project.

The financial support will be made by bank transfer in **two instalments**:

- **90%** of the value following the award of the funding and submission of the signed **Term of Acceptance**;
- **10%** following the submission of the **final report** (including description of the activities and

related costs).

Note: COESO may cancel the financial support attributed to the project due to non-compliance with the applicable regulations and commitments or in case of unjustified refusal to provide information that may be requested. In case of cancellation, applicants will refund the amounts received within 90 days from the date of receipt of the respective notification.

8. OPEN CALL CALENDAR

TIMEFRAME OF THIS CALL	
30 NOVEMBER 2021 TO 31 MARCH 2022 (17:00 CET)	
1st Round	
Short Proposal	
Proposal Submission	First day: 30 November 2021 Last Day: 30 January 2022 (17:00 CET)
Info Day	14 December 2022
Proposal Selection	1-14 February 2022
Notification of Proposal Selection	Last Day: 25 February 2022
2nd Round	
Full Project Proposal	
Proposal Submission	First Day: 2 March 2022 Last Day: 31 March 2022 (17:00 CET)
Mentoring Workshop	2 March 2022 (TBA)
Proposal Selection	1-20 April 2022
Notification of Proposal Selection	Last Day: 22 April 2022
Final Phase	
Start of the Projects	First Day: 1 June 2022 Last Day: 1 September 2022
End of the Projects	30 June 2023

9. OBLIGATIONS OF THE SELECTED PROJECTS

Selected projects are subject to the following obligations:

Communication and reporting obligations towards COESO

	WHAT	How / WHEN
Between the approval date and the start of the project	Term of Acceptance (Copy by e-mail and original by post)	To be sent by e-mail 10 business days after notification of approval
	Bank data	
	Invoice, receipt or an institutional declaration confirming reception of funds	To be sent by e-mail After reception of funds
	VERA Declaration of acceptance/commitment	To be sent by e-mail When submitting the full proposal project
During project implementation	Testing of VERA platform tools (by participating in focus groups, answering surveys, engaging in mutual learning exercises).	During the implementation phase and in line with the required by the COESO project
	Creation of a Blog on Hypotheses.org	During the implementation phase
After project completion	Final report (including description of the activities and related costs)	To be sent by e-mail 30 days after project completion
	Deliverables/products resulting from the project activities	To be sent by e-mail 30 days after project completion

Please note that it is mandatory that all the materials produced, in any formats, media or platforms, analogue or digital, used in the project activities (including future presentations not foreseen in the application) contain the following reference: "The xxx project/activity has received financial support from the European Commission EC-H2020-SWAFS Program (Science with and for Society), under Grant Agreement No. 101006325".

□ **Obligation to avoid conflict of interest**

Selected applicants must take all measures to prevent any situation where the impartial and objective implementation of the project is compromised for reasons involving economic interest, political or national affinity, family or emotional ties or any other shared interest ('conflict of interest').

Selected applicants will promptly notify CRIA and COESO in the event of any situation constituting or likely to lead to a conflict of interest and immediately take all the necessary steps to rectify this situation.

COESO and CRIA may verify whether the measures taken are appropriate and may require additional measures to be taken by a specified deadline.

If you have a prior relationship with anyone contributing to COESO/CRIA that you feel may constitute a conflict of interest, please send an e-mail to coeso.opencall@cria.org.pt for clarification.

10. DATA PROTECTION

COESO expects proposals to follow an open approach, sharing results and experiences widely with the community.

In addition, COESO or the European Commission may ask you to present your work as part of our public relations and networking events, in order to showcase the benefits of the COESO approach.

All proposals and related data, knowledge and documents will be treated according to the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) (Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016).

All personal data provided by the applicants will be processed by **CRIA** as the entity responsible for the data processing, exclusively for the purpose of these Call procedures.

CRIA undertakes to process the personal data of natural persons conveyed, obtained or made known to it under this Open Call, in compliance with the GDPR, including with regard to the exercise of data subjects' rights and the duties to provide the information referred to in Articles 13 and 14 of Chapter 3 of the GDPR, in particular taking into account the following:

a) Personal data will be processed in a manner that ensures its security, and prevents its

unauthorized disclosure or access;

- b) Personal data collection will be limited to what is strictly necessary for the intended purpose;
- c) Personal data collected for a specific purpose will not be processed in a way incompatible with that purpose;
- d) Personal data will not be stored any longer than necessary;
- e) Personal data will be processed lawfully, fairly and transparently in compliance with the applicable law;
- f) In the event of a personal data breach, the provisions of the GDPR will be applicable.

11. CONFIDENTIALITY

We will keep your proposal confidential, as well as any related information, data and documents we receive from you.

We will ensure that the process of handing and evaluating proposals is carried out in a confidential manner.

External experts are also bound by the duty of confidentiality.

You should also avoid taking any actions that could jeopardize confidentiality.

Your proposal is kept under secure conditions at all times. Application documentation will be kept for archiving or auditing purposes only.

Your proposal should not contain any information that is 'EU classified' under the rules on security of information in the Commission internal Rules of Procedure.

Information and documentation that is publicly available on the date it was obtained by COESO/CRIA or that COESO/CRIA are legally obliged to disclose under the law, court order or at the request of any regulatory authorities, are excluded from the duty of confidentiality established herein.

Please note that applications and their documents can be checked by the European Commission and/or its representatives. The European Commission may also, at any time, require more information or documents at its discretion.

12. SUPPORT AVAILABLE FOR APPLICANTS

Helpdesk

Applicants can ask questions via e-mail to coeso.opencall@cria.org.pt .

FAQ

A list of Frequently Asked Questions (FAQ) will be published and updated during the application period. Applicants are required to read the FAQ carefully before submitting the application or before submitting any question to the helpdesk.

Open Call Info Day and Webinar

An **Info Day** will be prepared during the application period for potential applicants to clarify any possible doubts regarding the application process.

A **Webinar** will be organised at the beginning of the 2nd round, to help the selected applicants to mentor their projects.

Further information related to Info Day and Webinar will be provided on the COESO website.

TEMPLATES

Short Proposal

Rules and guidelines

Applicants must use the template presented below, in which the following rules must be respected:

1. The template cannot be changed. When submitting, download a copy of this template, remove this cover page, and start answering the questions.
2. The proposal must have a maximum length of **3 pages**.
3. All questions must be answered. Leave the questions in.
4. Annexes are not allowed.
5. Links to your website or to previous work you have carried out are permitted. Links to external documents that answer a question are not allowed.
6. The budget must be for a maximum period of 12-months (minimum of 6 months).
7. The maximum amount available for funding is **€50,000.00** (for each of the 5 selected pilots).

Additional and useful notes:

1. Read the Guide for applicants and the FAQ before you start.
2. Be brief and to the point. This proposal is meant to convince the jury that your proposal deserves to be shortlisted.
3. Use specific examples whenever possible.
4. Be bold, but realistic. We want to fund projects that matter and that will be delivered.
5. All sections are important. Spend time on each of them.

Short Proposal

Fill in the title, acronym and keywords of your proposal below

Proposal title and acronym

Keywords (max 5 words):

List the type of participants (researcher, stakeholder), organization name and country

Type of participant	Organization name	Country

Please be specific, and provide only information that applies to the proposal and its objectives.

1. EXCELLENCE

1.1 Strength and innovation of the idea

- Describe the core idea of your application.
- What is new or different about it? Has it been tried before?

1.2 Relevance to the call

- What SDG² does your idea address?
- Which territories will the pilot cover?
- Is this your first citizen science project? Do you have expertise in project design, citizen engagement, data management, etc.?

1.3 Team

- What kind of stakeholders are involved? Who are the key stakeholders?
- Brief Bio (personal data of the academic and non-academic members - Title, surname, first name, full affiliation (department/centre, institution and e-mail address).

1.4 Data management

- What (if any) data do you intend to gather or produce? How much of this will be openly available?

2. IMPACT

2.1 Impact of the actions

- What problem/issue does your pilot address?

² More information about the SDG - <https://sdgs.un.org/goals>.

- *What will be the potential impact of the pilot on society/ the community / social targets?*

And on the production of new knowledge?

3. IMPLEMENTATION

3.1 Planned activities

- *Briefly describe the activities to be carried out.*

- *Which pilot activities will involve citizen science principles³?*

3.2 Project duration

- *Project start date and duration.*

3.3 Requested Total Budget

- *Briefly explain the main cost items (the requested budget must only be given in euros).*

³ See for example the ECSA Principles of Citizen Science:
<https://ecsa.citizen-science.net/2016/05/17/10-principles-of-citizen-science/>

Full Project Proposal

Rules and guidelines

Applicants must use the template presented below, in which the following rules must be respected:

8. The template cannot be changed. When submitting, download a copy of this template, remove this cover page, and start answering the questions.
9. The proposal must have a maximum length of **6 pages**.
10. All questions must be answered. Leave the questions in.
11. Annexes are not allowed.
12. Links to your website or to previous work you have carried out are permitted. Links to external documents that answer a question are not allowed.
13. The budget must be for a maximum period of 12-months (minimum of 6 months).
14. The maximum amount available for funding is **€50,000.00** (for each of the 5 selected pilots).

Additional and useful notes:

6. Read the Guide for applicants and the FAQ before you start.
7. Be brief and to the point. This proposal is meant to convince the jury that your proposal deserves to be shortlisted.
8. Use specific examples whenever possible.
9. Be bold, but realistic. We want to fund projects that matter and that will be delivered.
10. All sections are important. Spend time on each of them.

Full Project Proposal

Fill in the title, acronym and keywords of your proposal below

Proposal title and acronym

Keywords (max 5 words)

List the type of participants (researcher, stakeholder), organization name and country

Type of participant	Organization name	Country

Please be specific, and provide only information that applies to the proposal and its objectives.

1. EXCELLENCE

1.1 Strength and innovation of the idea

- *What is the main objective you would like to achieve with this pilot?*
- *What new ideas, concepts, approaches are brought in by the pilot?*

1.2 Relevance to the call

- *What expertise do you think you are missing? How could COESO help?*

1.3 Team

- *Who are the core members of your team? What are their relevant skills and experience?*
- *What kind of collaboration do you wish to implement in this pilot?*
- *How do the skills of the different core members complement each other for the success of the project?*

1.4 Data management

- *What other outputs will the pilot have? Which will be openly available?*
- *Does the proposed project require personal data? If so, how will you store this data? ⁴*

⁴ All pilots will be expected to comply with the General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679 (GDPR).

2. IMPACT

2.1 Impact of the actions

- *How can the proposal be carried out within the COESO vision/objectives?*
- *What are the end-benefits of your pilot? How will things be different at the end of the six months pilot? How about in a year, or in five years or a decade?*
- *Is this pilot an extension of an existing initiative? If so, what are the main outcomes?*
- *How is the action aligned with the European Citizen Science landscape?*

3. IMPLEMENTATION

3.1 Planned activities

- *Apart from the activities to be carried out, what other actions will your team participate in? (e.g., public dissemination, research publications, meetings with stakeholders, etc.)*
- *In what way does your project follow collaborative or participatory research methodology?*
- *How do you intend to attract and maintain the engagement of citizen scientists and other stakeholders after the end of the pilot?*
- *Indicate a list of deliverables or outcomes expected to be achieved (including a final report).*

3.2 Project duration (more detailed timeframe)

- *Project start date and duration (please provide details of timing for single activities)*

3.3 Total requested Budget

- *Explain the main cost items for each planned activity (the requested budget must only be given in euros).*

ANNEXES

Conflict of Interest Declaration Form

Please read the Open Call COESO-CALL-2021 Conflict of Interest Policy.

SECTION 1: PERSONAL DETAILS	
APPLICANT:	Click here to enter text.
APPLICATION ID:	Click here to enter text.
PHONE:	Click here to enter text.
EMAIL:	Click here to enter text.

SECTION 2: DISCLOSURE DETAILS <small>(Please complete in case you perceive the existence of an actual or potential conflict of interest)</small>
<p>The actual, potential or perceived conflict of interest relates to: <i>(tick all appropriate box/s)</i></p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Relationship with family or friends</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Relationship with external jury members</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Financial interest</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Gifts/benefits</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Relationship with COESO or CRIA</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Other (if you selected other, please provide details)</p>
<p>The following actual, potential or perceived conflict of interest has been identified <i>(please enter all relevant details)</i></p> <p>Click here to enter text.</p>
<p>The (actual, potential or perceived) conflict is expected to last: <i>(tick appropriate box)</i></p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 0–3 months <input type="checkbox"/> >3 months or ongoing</p>

SECTION 3: APPLICANT'S DECLARATION
<p>To the best of our knowledge and belief any actual, perceived or potential conflicts have been fully disclosed in this form in accordance with the requirements of the CRIA Conflict of Interest Policy.</p> <p>I acknowledge and agree to comply with the CRIA Conflict of Interest Policy and to promptly disclose any future perceived or potential conflict of interest.</p>
<p>SIGNATURE: _____ DATE: _____</p>

Declaration of Acceptance of participation in the Vera platform

Please read the Open Call COESO-CALL-2021 Declaration of Acceptance

SECTION 1: PERSONAL DETAILS	
APPLICANT:	Click here to enter text.
APPLICATION ID:	Click here to enter text.
PHONE:	Click here to enter text.
EMAIL:	Click here to enter text.

SECTION 2: COMMITMENT
<p>The Applicant hereby expressly accepts and undertakes to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Participate in the Vera Platform; Use VERA platform tools (by participating in focus groups, answering surveys, engaging in mutual learning exercises, etc.) whenever requested; Share the project implementation and results in accordance with the guidelines given to me by CRIA/COESO; Not to disclose to third parties the data accessed through the Vera Platform without the prior written consent of the respective holders.

SECTION 3: APPLICANT'S DECLARATION
<p>The participant also declares, for all due and legal purposes, that the personal data conveyed through Vera Platform have been obtained in accordance with the provisions in the General Data Protection Regulation.</p>
<p>SIGNATURE: _____</p>
<p>DATE: _____</p>